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Media and Political Interest: A Case Study on Media and Advertising Mars Party Perindo

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Abstract

Over a period of three years 2016-2018, (Multi Media Nusantara Cooperation (MNC), RCTI, MNCTV, and GTV received a reprimand from the Indonesian KPI due to the advertisement of Perindo mars politics that was considered to be excessive and troubling the public ahead of the 2019 elections. However, Harry Tanoesoedibjo, the owner of MNC Media and the chairman of the Perindo political party used his own media to achieve the political goals, and it was considered to be in conflict with the ideal function of the mass media in Indonesia. This research is qualitative, and uses constructive approach. Data were obtained through interviews, observation and literature review. In addition, Vincent Mosco's political, and economic theory with three frameworks was used, namely commodification, spatialization, structure, advertising and social responsibility press. The results of this study revealed the data causes, and the use of MNC Media as a political tool by Perindo parties in the form of advertisements, which have an impact on the society. The authorities can freely use theirs for personal (political) interests, while still within the corridors of rules and regulations in the country. Furthermore, it conclude that its uses is indeed very important in the context, but in reality, it does not have much influence on the political choices of the people in the 2019 elections, and it is clear that Perindo party election results only attained 27%.

Keywords: Political Advertising, Political Economy of Media, Press Social Responsibility

Introduction

The mass media using information and communication technology offer the benefits of fast, accurate and educative event (Briandana et al., 2020; Graber & Dunaway, 2018). Furthermore, its speed can also be spread to a heterogeneous audience in a manufacturing and distribution companies and impact industrial society (Gebner, 1967; Jenkins et al., 2018; Lindlof & Taylor, 2017; Nurudin, 2011). In addition, it also relates to the functions of information, sustainability, correlation, mobilization, and entertainment (McQuail & Deuze, 2020; Morrison, 2010). It can be social, political, cultural and institutional tool that places great importance on economic profit (Ejupi et al., 2014; Graber & Dunaway, 2018; Schramm et al., 1971). However, In politics, the question of the

function of media reports has shifted not only for economic reasons but also a political privilege that benefits the owners.

According to Briandana & Mihardja (2020); Doktoralina et al. (2020); Hoynes (2019) mass media trends in terms of economic motivation is characterized by increasing rate and proportion of the program broadcast. Another is the news program impressions that are not in line with the media ethics (Wilkins & Christians, 2020), and It should respect moral values and principles of right or wrong (Altschull, 1990; Wilkins & Christians, 2020; Wright & Hinson, 2015). However, because of the economic importance of broadcasting a program in the mass media, the market factor, that is to say to survive, the role of the communication should practice the selling of professionalism, codes of ethics and the moral responsibility of journalism. Meanwhile, many politicians are interested in the media and tends to present news that are pro-government because they are political figure supporting the government. This is to prevent the masses from getting to know the truth of the information, and the content of the news. This is because they choose news that supports the government and doesn't offer the opposition a balance (Hyden & Okigbo, 2017; Yustitia et al., 2019), and it happens in Indonesia, especially during the general election, such as legislative, regional head, and presidential elections.

Politicians placed mass media in an important position after 1998 reform because of the results of the direct election which lead to the amendment of 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia Years of 2002 (UUD 1945). Furthermore, In Direct elections and every other level of the government, from regents, mayors, governors, and the president, the media plays an important role during the campaign. The owner of news television and electronic, Surya Paloh joined politics and established a new political party. Aburizal Bakrie (The owner of Bakrie Group affiliated with the Golongan Karya/Golkar Party) and Hary Tanoesoedibjo (CEO/Chairman of Media Nusantara Citra/MNC Group established Perindo party. However, out of the three political parties, the most recent party formed in 2015 uses advertisements and, broadcast on television for the 2019 election.

The method by which Perindo makes it easily known to the public is through a massive performance of political song. However, Mars is broadcasted on various television media associated with the MNC Group, and it shows the high frequency of advertisements displayed, which include 20 spots per day, and as shown in the following table:

Table 1. Data summary of Mars Perindo's toward of KPI reprimands 2016-2018

Years	Description KPI Warning	Spot on	Duration
2016	First Pre-warning	13 times	7 minutes 25 seconds
	First Post-warning	7 times	7 minutes
2017	The Second Pre-warning	13 times	7 minutes 30 seconds
	The Second Post-warning	-	-
2018	The Third Pre-warning	12 times	8 minutes
	The Third Post-warning	6 times	6 minutes

Source: Data Processed (2019)

Due to the routine advertisement in table 1, Perindo received the attention of the Indonesian Broadcasting Commission (KPI) and that was considered to be a violation of the public interest. However, the declaration of violations submitted by the KPI was rejected by the Perindo general Secretary (kompas.com, 2017; Pedoman Perilaku Penyiaran (P3) Dan Standar Program Siaran, 2012). The party then explained that the ad contained no campaign, but was limited to socialization because Perindo was a new party that needed to be accepted by the public (www.cnnindonesia.com, 2018). Furthermore, MNC Media Group continues to serve Mars advertisement by reducing the intensity, and have a big role to play in filtering out what is good and not for the public and how people should behave.

In several elections, such as Belgium, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia as stated by André, Depauw, Shugart, & Chytilék (2017); Czada & Windhoff-Héritier (2019), the march strategy introduced by Perindo in the media, is a

good way to inform the public, and also provide prospect of election on the long run and foster party reputation. However, the interests of institutions or groups clash with press ethics and the ideology of the mass media, especially with regard to regulations and the needs of the community (Golding & Murdock, 2018; Iggers, 2018). The problem is, what are the factors that led to the emergence of media dynamics and political interests in the MNC Media case and the Perindo mars adverts? Second, how does Perindo uses mars ads for political purposes? Third, what is the dynamics of the media and the political interests of the MNC Media case and the Perindo mars?

2. Literature Review

2.1 *Political Economy of Media*

The political economy of the media as an institution has the power to influence the public (Sullivan, 2019). Furthermore, the principle of capitalist industrial system of mass media on production and distribution need to considered. Bettig (2018); Innis (2018) stated that mass media have economic, financial, political & culture consequences. For example, production and distribution systems, with regard to media properties, information practices, industry and radio dynamics, television, film and advertising have global economic-political inter-relationships.

Theoretically, political-economic, blames media ownership for people's reaction (Bardoel et al., 2005; Klaehn et al., 2018). In addition, the contents of media are commodities to be sold in the market, and the distribution of information is regulated according to the requirements. Although, this system refers to conservative and harmless activities, due to the exclusion of programs and dominant media channels, the relationship between economic structure and the dynamics of the media industry and ideology content is significant to the economic and the political system. However, If the impact on the decline of the independent media source affecting the concentration of the audience is avoided, then the negative investors in media are reduced (Bardoel et al., 2005). According to Jamil et al. (2019); Mosco & Nagy(2017; Nichols & Martínez (2019) considering political economy of communication from two angles, namely a special (narrow) and broad (general) perspective. From the narrow point of view, communication is defined as the study of social relations, in particular the power relations associated in the production, distribution, and consumption systems of resources. However, the general definition is about the control and survival in social life. Mosco & Nagy (2017) distinguish three political economy framework conditions, namely commodification, which is the process of transforming use values into exchange values, Spatialization as the process of overcoming the constraints of space and time in social life and Structuration that is regarding the idea relation between community agents, social processes and practices in an analysis.

2.2 *Advertisement*

Russell & Lane, (2001) stated that advertising serves as non-personal communication across different media, with the primary purpose of influencing audience behavior reading the content of a message. In Addition,Cant, Strydom, Jooste, & du Plessis, 2009; Kotler, Keller, Ang, Tan, & Leong, 2017) explained that advertising include all forms of presentation that support, promote ideas and goods. However, Burkhalter, Curasi, Thornton, & Donthu (2017); Percy & Rossiter (1992) reported the need for creative concepts that support one another such as heard words, Color, Music, Picture, seen words and Movement elements.

2.3 *Press Theory and the Press System*

Siebert, Siebert, Peterson, Peterson, & Schramm (1956) distinguish four types of press theory, namely Authoritarian, Libertarian, Social Responsibility, and the Soviet communist concepts. However, in Indonesia, Social Responsibility Theory is generally used. The assumption underlying this theory is that freedom bears the same responsibility, with the press being responsible for informing, educating and promoting society. As such, the media play a role in reflecting diversity and gaining access to views from different perspectives. Furthermore, public opinion, ethics, and consumer reaction are therefore in the control of press performance.

The Country, guarantee the freedom of the press by the fifth amendment of the 1945 constitution in clause 28 (Rendra, 2005: 278). However, the essential differences in media on social responsibility theory as described by Siebert et al., (1956) outlined the need for a commitment to social responsibility for community opinion, consumer behavior and professional ethics. The most important aspect is that the media are forced to fulfill their social obligations, and failure to do will therefore affect its constraint (Ardianto, 2009; Center et al., 2008; Wrong, 2017).

2.4 Theoretical Framework

This research identifies the political ads from Perindo mars which will be broadcast on MNC Media owned by Harry Tanoesoedibjo the chairman, which is considered as a "political tool" described in the following figure:

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework for thinking on media power and political interests
Source: Data Proessed (2019)

3. Method

This research is a qualitative study with a constructive paradigm. Data were obtained through interviews, observation and literature review. Furthermore, it uses an in-depth explanatory case, which examine the role of Perindo and MNC groups with the continuous use of (Mars) political song for advertisement, and campaign, However, it was conducted jn 2018-2019, before and during the 2019 Election.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Economics and Politics of Mass Media

According to Mosco (2015); Mosco & Nagy (2017), commodification, is an attempt by the mass media to change everything so that it can be used as a lucrative tool for content, audiences, and employees.

The content is commercialized to attract audience attention and is tied to placement of advertisements (due to the large number of viewers participating in a program), which generates revenue for the company. However, Mars Perindo has significant public information value by introducing elements of political parties and other activities. It is an exchange rate that can be sold to the public via television channels and advertising with a creative element.

Audience marketing is made clear by the collaboration between multinationals and advertisers. It is the largest and most popular national private television channel with great diversity, good ratings, performance and very good stability. It has credibility with target audience segments and many loyal viewers.

Price Time	Non Prime Time	All Time	Average Sun-Mon (Week):
SCTV: 19.7 (-0.4)	IVM: 18.3 (3.1)	IVM: 17.5 (3.5)	IVM: 16.8 (1.8)
IVM: 15.5 (4.2)	SCTV: 13.9 (-3.1)	SCTV: 15.6 (-2.4)	SCTV: 16.2 (-1)
RCTI: 15 (-1.6)	RCTI: 12.5 (-0.2)	RCTI: 13.2 (-0.7)	RCTI: 13.8 (-0.5)
TRANS7: 11.6 (1.7)	MNCTV: 12.3 (1.7)	MNCTV: 12 (0.7)	MNCTV: 12.6 (0.9)
MNCTV: 11.3 (-1.6)	TRANS7: 10.9 (2.9)	TRANS7: 11.1 (2.5)	TRANS7: 9.7 (1.6)
ANTV: 7.6 (-0.5)	GTV: 9 (-1)	ANTV: 8.5 (-1.5)	ANTV: 9 (-1)
TRANS: 6.5 (-0.9)	ANTV: 8.9 (-2)	GTV: 8.1 (-1)	GTV: 7.3 (-1.3)
GTV: 6.1 (-0.8)	TRANS: 8.1 (-0.6)	TRANS: 7.6 (-0.7)	TRANS: 7.3 (-0.4)
TVONE: 2.4 (0)	TVONE: 2.3 (-0.6)	TVONE: 2.3 (-0.5)	TVONE: 2.7 (-0.1)
METRO: 1.6 (0)	TVRI1: 1.6 (0.4)	TVRI1: 1.5 (0.2)	TVRI1: 2 (0.3)
INEWS: 1.4 (0)	INEWS: 1.2 (-0.3)	INEWS: 1.3 (-0.2)	INEWS: 1.5 (0)
TVRI1 1.3 (-0.1)	METRO: 1 (-0.3)	METRO: 1.2 (-0.1)	METRO: 1.2 (-0.2)

Source: Data Processed (2019)

The commodification of workers was carried out when work done was eliminated, therefore the pay slips can be manipulated and deducted correctly. However, the commercialization of MNC Media and Perindo employees is a symbol of mutualism between companies. Furthermore, Perindo utilizes media workers techniques for the march production process and screening. If the MNC Media employees are deployed by Perindo, it certainly add to the profit with the cost of production and advertising, and also the higher the profit, but technically the workload is greater than what it is should. The commodification of these findings can be seen in the following table:

Table. 3. Coomodification

Commodification	Detection
Content	Interesting and informative ad content Have educational value that is sold to the public. Advertising which is an income for the company
Audiens	Television stations with good ratings and shares have good credibility for the public Ads are on watches that have a good rating and share
Worker	Technical utilization of workers Pressing production costs The company's income is getting bigger

Source: Data Processed (2019)

Next is spatialization, where media owners use technology to overcome distance and time to maximize work and increase profits. There is also an horizontal integration, which means that a company has to develop its business in various fields, and vertical integration, which is a control effort made by media owners, in order to equate work ideology.

Spatialalization which includes the space and time used by Perindo and MNC Media utilizes an institutional structure, like Harry Tanoesoedibjo position as the owner. The power of ownership, networking and the speed of the negotiation process of advertising through a holding company are easier and faster. Ease of access to space and time of products broadcast by the media to the public, considering that MNC Media is a national television that has reached all parts of Indonesia, it is certain that people easily watch the Perindo Mars advertisement. MNC Media corporation which has been established for decades to gain space and trust in public broadcast program. Furthermore, several television stations display the same advertising content (monopoly of the impressions), this is considered to be more profitable for Perindo. This can be seen on the table below.

Table 4. Spatialalization

Vertical		Horizontal	
Name	Type	Name	Type
RCTI TV	Televisi	Holding	Integrasi
MNC TV	Televisi		
Global TV	Televisi		

Source: Data processed (2019)

The structuring is a continuation of the form of vertical integration in spatialization. However, according to Giddens structure, it influence each other activities in the mass media due to different access possibility between workers and capital owners.

This shows in the power of Harry Tanoesoebidjo's the owner of MNC Media, and Perindo. Having full control on the media and others within, in order to equalize the work ideology. However, this was done by the party in the intensity for frequent Mars advertisements, with the power possessed by Harry Tanoesoebidjo, MNC Media which was considered as a procedures and bureaucracy of ad serving at a television station, was able to comply with the rules and regulations of the supervisory institutions, and ultimately to stun the masses. with Mars Perindo.

4.2 *Song of Political Parties (Mars) Perindo as Political Party Advertising*

According to Wright & Hinson (2015) advertising is a communication process that plays a very important role as a marketing tool that helps in selling of goods, and services, as well as ideas through certain channels in the form of information. Furthermore, it is used for variety of purposes, including political parties, during its development. However, a creative advertising concept has elements that support each other. The mutually supportive idea is the words heard in the advertisements that are displayed, making the viewers understand more about the purpose (Percy & Rossiter, 1992).

Mars Perindo advertisements, is considered to have an implicit meaning as stated by Jamil & Hesti (2019); Percy & Rossiter (1992) This can be seen from the arrangement of words and related sentences that form "Mars Perindo ". In addition, the choice of words that listeners easily remember, the sentence of an invitation to a high sense of nationalism, vision, mission and the lyrics of the song, are considered complete to make the public understand the goals set by the party.

Perindo harmonized the color elements for the image, setting the light in the display of advertising impressions, a mixture of natural images that are art of beauty are combined with the activities. While the colors are technically combined in the shot, there is a very different subject specification between landscape beauty photography and grouping of models according to radio and television standards that meet the technical requirements to be eligible for advertisement.

In addition, regarding the music, the Mars Perindo advertisement, which was unwittingly broadcast for three years, familiarized the public with musical instruments, even though they were only played with or without words for the first five seconds. However, instruments with national nuances and orchestra accompaniments have their own standards and are easily recognized. Including the object, model, and the scene displayed in the landscape beauty shoot image with Perindo activities and its characters, the picture is also arranged into a complete and interesting whole and pleases the eyes of the audience to continue watching until the end of the advertisement. Furthermore, the final message can be finally passed on to the public.

Another thing that also becomes the mainstay of the show is the element of words, which appear on the advertisement impressions that affect the image of the product in the minds of viewers after the first 5 seconds. This often draws the public's eye to the writing, which creates a memorized effect with the slogan, vision and mission of the party. Coupled with the clear display of graphics, logos and writing at the end of the mars for 3

seconds, this is enough to grab the attention of the audience, because the duration of the show is long enough to read and understand the message conveyed by Marsindo.

As for the element of movement, they exist, and are seen in advertising impressions that affect people's emotions which uses angles to make Mars look attractive. Images that have a significant "good cause" are often shown, such as people in need, health facilities, providing means of transportation for the community, scholarships, aid to wagon used for businesses, and agricultural produce. These "good" things are displayed almost from the beginning to the end of Mars with a duration of 30 to 60 seconds. It certainly evokes the emotions of the audience that Perindo has an advantageous vision and mission to help the people of Indonesia.

For this reason, Mars Perindo is seen as a full advertisement on both audio and video for a political party, which is attractive and very familiar to all Indonesians. Furthermore, the three functions of political advertising are First to persuade and convince the public in making their choices. Second, to identify or differentiate between one candidate from another. Third, to provide information on vision (ideological view that is used as a reference in acting), mission (actions or practices to use power resources), and various programs (political concepts that are operationalized, are measured mathematically). In addition, the Perindo's march ad has many versions that are frequently broadcasted on national private television stations under the auspices of MNC Media (RCTI, MNC TV, and GTV). The effect of Perindo's creative advertising strategy by Kasali (1995:83-86) stated that a good advert must meet up with the criteria of AIDCA (Attention, Interest, Desire, Conviction and Action) to avoid the violation of advertising ethics.

In the political context, every party have a certain strategy, game plan, and purpose for their success. One of the methods used by Perindo through Mars is that it has managed to attract public attention. The presence of the Marshall Perindo ad is considered to have reached this stage. The people who were brainwashed during the Perindo walk were remembered and considered good - although this was ultimately seen as a disruptive effect. However, the owner of MNC Media's and Chairman of Perindo, Harry Tanoesoedibjo has eventually become a problem, therefore MNC Media is considered not to be a neutral mass media, because it shows that it is in the interest of a group.

Taking a closer look at the advertising strategy, the authors note that Perindo's Mars advertising level is considered overwhelming for people who have reached the phase of interest, but the results achieved during the 2019 election was just 2.8%. This proves that such an effort made by the party in advertising in many national mass media only reaches the phase of Interest, And does not follow the desire, necessity, conviction and action. However, the performance of Perindo was below expectations and contradicts the efforts made, which made only few people to choose the party. This in turn indicates that, there will be different views in the political sphere of advertising and media. Furthermore, when people are associated with political choices, they are considered "wise" in their decisions. In this case the public only deals with consequences rather the objectives of a political party. More clearly it can be seen on the table below:

Table. 5. Achievement of Mars Perindo's Advertising Strategy

Description	Detection
<i>Attention</i>	V
<i>Interest</i>	V
<i>Desire</i>	X
<i>Conviction</i>	X
<i>Action</i>	X

Source: Data processed (2019) refer to the Ad Strategy according to Kasali (1995)

The foundations of existing institutions in Indonesia are rules, including the Act to Support Broadcasting Policy. The problem with Perindo ads is that there are no regulations that violate the rules, such as the rule that media owners can only participate in politics if excessive advertising content is involved, and they money to get one to display the ad on a public frequency. However, the frequency of the show is regularly taken into account, which has a negative impact on the community, especially on children.

4.3 *Mass Media Social Responsibility*

Since the government uses regulations No. 40/1999, normatively, the press in Indonesia has adopted the theory of social responsibility (freedom of the press which is responsible to the public/public interest). The system has experienced dynamics along with the movement of modern politics. During the nationalist movement, the media was seen as a struggle tool, and During the independence, the press had become a tool for the struggle of political parties. However, after stability and development, the media played a role in the context of communication and commodities (the capitalist press). Today, they are in the context of freedom and commercialization.

The emerging reality is that the press becoming profit-oriented, which places more emphasis on sales and advertising than the need of the public with comprehensive and accurate information about the threat to morals, violation of personal rights and the control of socioeconomic class, business that endangers the market idea, which is free and open. The current state of the press system in Indonesia is inextricably linked to the influence and interference of the rule of a handful of capital owners in the newspaper industry, which is also part of the penetration and expansion of capitalism and global political power.

In this case, Harry Tanoesoedibjo who is affiliated with Perindo political party, has dominated shows in the MNC Media. Perindo advertisements are unconsciously consumed publicly using existing channels in media conglomerates. However, mass media capitalism in MNC Media welcomes political power and at present, many Indonesian press actors are misinterpreting their freedom. Many factors influence it, such as the impact of globalization, adoption of the market system, the absence of referrals for members, society, government and implementation of a free and responsible press.

The importance of press freedom which is ideally has to do with the interests of the public, is now displaced by the powerful factors of globalization and increasing evolving technology. The function of the media as an information tool is considered as void for Perindo, which feels the need to be informed is to attract attention of the public. Even with the use of media functions, the efforts also overlap with existing regulations in Indonesia which is considered lax and allow it to carry out its political efforts. However, in the case of campaigns advocating for socialization, political content, education and nationalism for the community, as well as other strategies that have been defined by regulations, such as the elaboration of vision and mission in song lyrics, implied party elements and musical instruments that are tricked in such a way that the regulations are treated as if they have no place to judge.

This proves that the theory of social responsibility is difficult to implement, due to the complexity of the standoff between the interests of the government and the owners or workers involved. This system is therefore at the interface between the authoritarian and libertarian. In order words, the government steps in to articulate the functions, duties and authority of the media as an expression of its responsibility. However, this system an authoritarianism. On the other hand, the system evolve towards liberalism of the workers and formulate it independently.

Social responsibility theory states that anyone who has something important to say must be given rights in the forum, and if the media is deemed not fulfilling its obligations, there are those that should enforce it. According to this theory, they are controlled by public opinion, consumer action, professional code of ethics, and in the case of broadcasting, by the regulatory authority, taking into account the technical limitations of the media, and number of available frequency channels (Siebert et al., 1956).

In this case, however, public statements are still limited by existing regulations, and not all forms of expression can be published by the media in the forums provided. Like the people who have the right to protest and even punish the press/mass media harming the community. The public may protest or punish the mass media for reporting false news or events and it can be carried out directly by sending a letter of protest to the mass media, or by reporting to the relevant institution such as the press council and KPI. However, its role in, the state, and society is to mutually sustain the country's progress.

In practice, this is done by the community, but based on the rules contested by the interests of the political parties Perindo. A regulations with various types of wings as the basis for regulating the media in Indonesia could not act decisively, and the interests of groups in the mass media may still exist under the pretext that they follow the rules. determined by the state.

In this case, the authors assume that this is seen from two approaches. First, the rule-based states that provided none of the things that violate the rules or regulations in this case are determined by the laws in Indonesia and Ethics of advertising, then it is safe because the existing rules oblige offenders to do otherwise. Second, an ethical approach which means utilizing the public frequency for personal interests or certain groups and its existence is not good in a media management. However, they does not allow owners to intervene procedurally and that follows the established bureaucracy. There is a sense of proportionality, which principles speak of ethics and conscience, not just technical, and this is a sign that cannot be avoided in Indonesia, due to possible regulations.

5. Conclusion

The ownership between MNC Media and Perindo as a powerhouse is the most important factor influencing the issue. However, the existence of a conflicting interest in the phenomenon of mass media is at the origin of ideology, which is never separated from economic and political factors. Instead of taking the interests of the public into account, owners always prioritize profits, along with the development of modern information and communication technology. In terms of advertising, media is used as a marketing tool for products and services, also for political parties purposes and as a means of socialization in order to gain public attention in the context of the 2019 election. Furthermore, the economic factors to which the industry belongs, aims at generating much income and profit as possible in order to maintain the competitive market, the rating and the proportion that a national private television considers credible to the public with technical benefits and political factors and that clearly show the role of Harry Tanoe the owner of MNC Media and chairman of the Perindo political party utilizing his property for personal/group interests (Perindo party) directly through holding and integration to achieve political goals.

The advertisement of Perindo march is with a complete and attractive package, which is a means of socialization for the political party. However, there are no conflicts with regard to the law, but at the end the principle of political ethics is expected to be a control for media owners as well as a consideration for regulators or regulatory bodies to be more assertive. The efforts made by the Perindo party in the political strategy that dominates the MNC mass media, apparently are not directly proportional to the objectives of the political party. The results of the 2019 election showed that Perindo only achieved 2.7%, and it can be practically proven that the party is only successful in the phase of advertising strategies of public interest, but has not reached the final stage of good advertising strategy, namely action. Therefore there is a need for good, dynamic, clear and firm regulations. This research is therefore useful in order to invite all media owners to pay close attention to the position of the mass media in the community, which is intended for the society. This study does not address the psychological consequences of a free and profit-oriented press, public morals and the violation of personal rights and socio-economic class control that can undermine the free and open market of ideas. Further research should therefore link the theory of market behavior and its effects on the economy and firms using quantitative measures.

References

- 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, 22 (2002).
- Altschull, J. H. (1990). *From Milton to McLuhan The Ideas Behind American Journalism*.
- André, A., Depauw, S., Shugart, M. S., & Chytilék, R. (2017). Party nomination strategies in flexible-list systems: Do preference votes matter? *Party Politics*, 23(5), 589–600.
- Ardianto, E. (2009). *Public Relations Praktis* (Februari 2). Widya Padjadjaran.
- Bardoel, J., McQuail, D., Golding, P., & de Bens, E. (2005). „*Beyond Journalism: A Profession Between Information Society And Civil Society* “. Sage, London.
- Bettig, R. V. (2018). *Copyrighting culture: The political economy of intellectual property*. Routledge.
- Briandana, R., Doktoralina, C. M., Hassan, S. A., & Hasan, W. N. W. (2020). Da'wah Communication and Social Media: The Interpretation of Millennials in Southeast Asia. *International Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 8(1), 216–226. <https://www.ijeba.com/journal/543>
- Briandana, R., & Mihardja, E. J. (2020). Consumer Journey and Social Media : The Content Management of E-Catering Marketplace Promotion Media For SME Catering Services Business Industry. *International Journal of Communication Research*, 10(1), 83–91.
- Burkhalter, J. N., Curasi, C. F., Thornton, C. G., & Donthu, N. (2017). Music and its multitude of meanings: Exploring what makes brand placements in music videos authentic. *Journal of Brand Management*, 24(2), 140–160.
- Cant, M. C., Strydom, J. W., Jooste, C. J., & du Plessis, P. J. (2009). *Marketing management*. Juta and Company Ltd.
- Center, A. H., Jackson, P., Smith, S., & Stansberry, F. R. (2008). *Public relations practices: Managerial case studies and problems*. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Czada, R. M., & Windhoff-Héritier, A. (2019). *Political Choice: Institutions, rules and the limits of rationality*. Routledge.
- Doktoralina, C. M., Bahari, Z., Hassan, S. A., Ismail, N. A., & Mardiyah, S. A. L. (2020). Hashtags as a way to expedite the zakat supply chain. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 8(1), 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2019.7.004>
- Ejupi, V., Siljanovska, L., & Iseni, A. (2014). The mass media and persuasion. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(14), 636–646.
- Gebner, G. (1967). *Mass Media and Human Communication Theory*. Editor: FEX Dance. New York: Holt, Rinehart, & Winston.
- Golding, P., & Murdock, G. (2018). Ideology and the mass media: the question of determination. In *Routledge Revivals: Ideology and Cultural Production (1979)* (pp. 198–224). Routledge.
- Graber, D. A., & Dunaway, J. (2018). *Mass media and American politics* (Tenth Edit). Cq Press.
- Hoynes, W. (2019). *Public television for sale: Media, the market, and the public sphere*. Routledge.
- Hyden, G., & Okigbo, C. (2017). The media and the two waves of democracy. In *Media and democracy in Africa* (pp. 29–53). Routledge.
- Iggers, J. (2018). *Good news, bad news: Journalism ethics and the public interest*. Routledge.
- Innis, H. A. (2018). *Political economy in the modern state*. University of Toronto Press.
- Jamil, A., & Hesti, S. (2019). New Political Party and Political Branding: Perindo for Prosperous Indonesia. *First International Conference on Administration Science (ICAS 2019)*, 449–453. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icas-19.2019.93>
- Jamil, A., Rekart, E., Briandana, R., & Audinna, S. (2019). The Role of Social Media Hashtags in Political Promotions : Mediating Role of Supply Chain Communication. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 8(6), 181–188.
- Jenkins, H., Ford, S., & Green, J. (2018). *Spreadable media: Creating value and meaning in a networked culture* (Vol. 15). NYU press.
- Kasali, R. (1995). Manajemen periklanan. In *Jakarta: Grafiti*.
- Klaehn, J., Broudy, D., Fuchs, C., Godler, Y., Zollmann, F., Chomsky, N., Pedro-Carañana, J., Mills, T., & Boyd-Barrett, O. (2018). Media theory, public relevance and the propaganda model today. *Media Theory*, 2(2), 164–191.
- kompas.com. (2017, May 13). MNC Ditegur soal Iklan, Perindo Sebut KPI Salah Alamat. <https://Nasional.Kompas.Com>, 1.
- Kotler, P., Keller, K. L., Ang, S. H., Tan, C. T., & Leong, S. M. (2017). *Marketing management: an Asian perspective* (6th editio). Pearson.
- Lindlof, T. R., & Taylor, B. C. (2017). *Qualitative Communication Research Methods* (Fourth Edi). Sage publications. <https://us.sagepub.com/en-us/nam/qualitative-communication-research-methods/book239370>
- McQuail, D., & Deuze, M. (2020). *Media and Mass Communication Theory* (6 edition). SAGE Publications Limited.
- Morrison, M. A. (2010). Teori Komunikasi Massa: Media, Budaya, dan Masyarakat. In *Bogor: Penerbit Ghalia*

- Indonesia. Ghalia Indonesia.
- Mosco, V. (2015). The political economy of communication: A living tradition. In *Power, Media, Culture* (pp. 35–57). Springer.
- Mosco, V., & Nagy, I. (2017). Political Economy of Media Effects. *The International Encyclopedia of Media Effects*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118783764.wbieme0095>
- Nichols, R., & Martínez, G. (2019). *Political Economy of Media Industries: Global Transformations and Challenges*. Routledge. <https://books.google.co.id>
- Nurudin, N. (2011). *Pengantar Komunikasi Massa*. RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Percy, L., & Rossiter, J. R. (1992). A model of brand awareness and brand attitude advertising strategies. *Psychology & Marketing*, 9(4), 263–274.
- Pedoman Perilaku Penyiaran (P3) dan Standar Program Siaran, 96 (2012). http://www.kpi.go.id/download/regulasi/P3SPS_2012_Final.pdf
- Russell, J., & Lane, R. (2001). *Kleppner's advertising procedure* (15th Editi). Prentice Hall.
- Schramm, W., Schramm, W. L., & Roberts, D. F. (1971). *The process and effects of mass communication*. (2nd, revised ed.). University of Illinois Press. <https://books.google.co.id>
- Siebert, F., Siebert, F. T., Peterson, T. B., Peterson, T., & Schramm, W. (1956). *Four theories of the press: The authoritarian, libertarian, social responsibility, and Soviet communist concepts of what the press should be and do*. University of Illinois press.
- Sullivan, J. L. (2019). *Media audiences: Effects, users, institutions, and power*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated.
- Wilkins, L., & Christians, C. G. (2020). *The Routledge Handbook of Mass Media Ethics* (Second Edi). Routledge.
- Wright, D. K., & Hinson, M. D. (2015). Examining social and emerging media use in public relations practice: A ten-year longitudinal analysis. *Public Relations Journal*, 9(2), 1–26.
- Wrong, D. (2017). *Power: Its forms, bases and uses*. Routledge.
- www.cnnindonesia.com. (2018, March 23). *Perindo Langgar Aturan Beriklan Kampanye di Televisi*.
- Yustitia, S., Susilo, M., & Afifi, S. (2019). Opinion Polarisation in Indonesia Politics. *The 1st Asian Conference on Humanities, Industry, and Technology for Society, ACHITS 2019, 30-31 July 2019, Surabaya, Indonesia*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.4108/cai.30-7-2019.2287626>